

The Study of International Ecological Relations in Uzbekistan History

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Abstract: Analyzes the issues of studying the aspects of international cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the years of independence related to ecology and environmental protection. In particular, studies on the issues of improving the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region , climate change , water resources management, biodiversity conservation , and the development of regional cooperation on environmental protection in Central Asia are reflected. At the same time, the historiography of studies on the cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with international organizations is widely covered. Foreign publications covering certain aspects of the activities of international organizations, such as the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea , the Interstate Water Management Coordination Commission, and the Central Asian Regional Ecological Center, are also analyzed.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, Central Asia, international cooperation, ecology, transboundary rivers, historiography.

Introduction. During the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan , as an equal subject of international relations, has been paying attention to improving the important directions and legal foundations of international ecological political relations. In particular, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, organizational, legal and socio-economic measures to ensure environmental safety are being consistently implemented. The implementation of the rules of international legal treaties and conventions into national legislation has become one of the main issues . International cooperation relations in the field of ecology and environmental protection in the Republic of Uzbekistan are determined by the foreign policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan .

Literature analysis and methodology. The role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the system of international relations, environmental issues in the country's domestic and foreign policy activities, issues related to environmental protection and improvement of the ecological situation in the Central Asian region, including Uzbekistan, on the basis of international cooperation are one of the new directions in the modern historiography of the history of Uzbekistan. Taking into account the volume of research conducted on the problem under study and the created literature, it is expedient to conditionally divide them into two groups.

Among the literatures included in the first group, a number of works and dissertations created in Uzbekistan during the years of independence are of great importance. These include A. Kasimov, A. Halliev, Sunnah Don Gee, D. Misharev, The works of M. Rakhimov, E. Nuriddinov, H. Gulomov, A. Kholliiev, A. Kirgizboev, A. Sultanov, R. Asadova, D. Rakhimbayeva, N. Gafurov and other authors on the history of the development of the country's

foreign policy can be included. These works cover the formation of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an equal member of international relations, and the development processes in the first decade of independence.

Second group foreigner of the authors from his works consists of. They between Central Asian region A. Akimov, a historian, political scientist, and other scholars from the CIS countries who have conducted research related to I. Zvyagelskaya, V. Belokrinitsky, A. Kurtov, A. Perepelkin, D. Trofimov, S. Panarin, E. Safronova, O. Tikhonov, A. Kazantsev, A. Vlasov, D. Nishanov , S. Yun , E. Troitsky, A. Bogaturov, A. Taylakova and others work in studying the problem separately arouses interest.

The application of the principle of objectivity in research allows to minimize and eliminate the impact of subjective views on the research and its results as much as possible in the interpretation and assessment of evidence. From this point of view, the principles of historicity, scientificity and objectivity, which constitute the dialectical basis of scientific knowledge, are the theoretical methodological bases of the research, and the methods of historical-comparison, systematization, problem-chronological and interdisciplinary approach were used.

Analysis and results. To date, a number of studies have been conducted in various fields of social sciences , including history, law , philosophy, and political science, focusing on global environmental problems such as the development of regional cooperation on environmental protection in Central Asia, strengthening good - neighborly relations with countries in the region , eliminating transboundary problems , improving the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region , climate change, water resources management , and biodiversity conservation .

It is important that various aspects of the environmental situation in Uzbekistan are covered in a group of literature . For example, publications in the fields of ecology, law, and political science provide information on Uzbekistan's environmental policy, the implementation of its obligations under international treaties, and Uzbekistan's foreign policy. There are a number of sources on the ecology and environment sector that cover issues related to the international environmental cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan . In particular, the books “Population Health and Environmental Problems” by D. Bobojonova, “Fundamentals of Ecology and Nature Protection” by Kh. Tursunov, “Ecology and Culture” by B. Kalonov, B. Ziyamukhamedov, “Ecology and Law” by J. Kholmuminov, “Ecology” by A. Tokhtaev, “What is Ecology?” by A. Nigmatov, “Ecology Economics” by T. M. Zhumaev, “Problems of Regional Ecology Regulation” by N. Ikramova, and “Human Ecology” by A. Ergashev cover in detail the impact of environmental problems on population health , the role of the human factor in environmental protection , the legal solution of environmental issues in legislation , and the issues of cooperation between social institutions and non-governmental non-profit organizations in stabilizing the ecological situation . Recent studies in this area have examined the current ecological situation in the country and the environmental problems that have arisen in this process .

In scientific literature, monographs, doctoral dissertations and scientific research works in the field of political science, the current ecological situation in the country in recent years and the global ecological problems that have arisen in this process have been discussed. The book “The Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan and Electoral Legislation” by J. Kholmuminov, D. Umarov, “Human and Environmental Factors” by Sh. Babayev, “Environmental Policy and Safety” by B. Aslonov, N. Karimova, “Ecological Monitoring of Some Areas of Uzbekistan and Morbidity” by E. Danilova, “Ecological Policy of the State. Concept of Legal Protection” by Sh. Faiziev, “On Measures to Promote Ecological Culture Among the Population” by A. Sanginov, opinions on issues of international environmental relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan were expressed.

Legal studies cover the normative and legal aspects of the tasks of protecting nature and the environment in the country, and improving the overall ecological situation . Representatives of this field include T. Mirzaev 's textbook " Checking the implementation of environmental laws

and eliminating violations of laws", B. Kalonov's book "State bodies implementing environmental control and their powers", D. Safarov's scientific research work "Issues of systematization and codification of environmental legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan ", J. Kholmuminov, within the framework of his research on topical issues of the history of Uzbekistan, touched upon the political, economic , and cultural life of the country and issues of international cooperation in these areas , analyzed the historical foundations of the socio-ecological problems that have arisen, and the causes of their emergence. At the same time, some information on issues of international environmental cooperation is also found in published scientific and popular scientific works.

At the same time, in the publications published in the economic sphere in our republic, O. Khamidov's articles "Improving the management mechanism for the development of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan", F. Valieva's "Global problems of ecology" and N. Samigova's "Ecological consequences of urbanization and industrialization of modernity", A. Umarov's "Ecological aspects of increasing the efficiency of using the economic potential of the region" and G. Rakhimova's scientific research works "The impact of industrial development of the Fergana Valley on the ecological situation in the 50s-90s of the 20th century" have also reflected information on Uzbekistan's environmental policy, the implementation of obligations under international treaties, and Uzbekistan 's foreign policy in economic research .

It is important to highlight the research of the country's historical scientists on various issues of the new and most recent history of Uzbekistan. These scientific studies analyze the historical foundations of socio-ecological problems that have arisen in our republic, their causes and solutions .

D. Bobojonova's research works "Socio-economic factors of the development of interethnic relations in Uzbekistan" [1], H. Yunusova's "Socio-economic processes and spiritual life of Uzbekistan in the 80s of the 20th century" [2], and B. Isakov's "The impact of historical changes in Uzbekistan in the second half of the 80s - 2000s on demographic processes" [3] reflect the demographic processes of Uzbekistan, namely, changes in the areas of birth, natural population growth and migration, issues related to external labor migration in connection with the growth of the number of labor resources, and the issue of raising a harmonious generation in Uzbekistan in the spirit of interethnic harmony and tolerance. Because the main directions of international cooperation on nature protection are determined by the principles of the foreign policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan (national-state interests of the country, norms of international law, non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries, peaceful resolution of all disputes) .

O. Kamilov's scientific research work entitled "Development of the Irrigation System in Uzbekistan and Its Consequences (1951-1990)" [4] discusses the numerous constructions of hydraulic structures in Uzbekistan during the years of Soviet rule, the fact that they mainly served to improve the republic's cotton sector, and the underlying issue was the policy of cotton monopoly, and the rational use of transboundary river waters in Central Asia, taking into account the increasing scarcity of water resources, the conclusion of agreements aimed at improving the technical condition and efficiency of existing large hydraulic structures, ensuring their safety, and reducing their negative impact on the environment and the lives of the population, and their practical application. At the same time, taking into account that water is a source of life, today, in order to establish rational and effective use of its resources and introduce the drip irrigation method into the agricultural sector of all countries in the region, it was suggested to develop and sign agreements under the initiative of authoritative international organizations, to establish and launch the Central Asian Interstate Water Management Commission to prevent and eliminate drinking water shortages and ensure and eliminate the associated food security.

In his scientific research work entitled "The Environmental Situation and Its Social Problems in Uzbekistan in the Second Half of the 20th Century - the Beginning of the 21st Century"[5], S. Davletov emphasized the expediency of forming an environmental history society in the

Republic of Uzbekistan, the need for a more in-depth study of the relationship between nature and society, and the introduction of special courses "Fundamentals of Sustainable Development and Nature Use" into the curricula of history, ecology, economics, and agriculture in higher educational institutions to improve environmental knowledge and skills. In addition, taking into account the importance of the widespread introduction of renewable energy technologies in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, it is necessary to increase targeted projects that promote the technical capabilities and socio-economic effects of the effective use of alternative energy sources and resource-saving technologies, and, taking into account the increasing demand for food in connection with the dynamic growth of the population in the country and further improvement of the well-being of the population, effectively use innovative and resource-saving technologies in agriculture, and further strengthen the integration of science and production .

M. Rakhimov's D.M. Rahimbaeva's "The history of the formation and development of the diplomatic service in Uzbekistan (1944-2001. The example of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs)" and D. Sayfullaev's scientific research work "The Formation and Development of Uzbek Diplomacy during the Period of Independence" [6] specifically addresses the issues of international environmental cooperation, taking into account the changing nature of international relations and international politics , and discusses the development of integration processes between the countries of Central Asia, as well as joint solutions to emerging social, economic, and especially environmental problems. Also in this group, it is possible to highlight the research on the cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with international organizations .

M. Rakhimov's "Mejdunarodnoe sotrudnichestvo Uzbekistana v kontekte obespecheniya stabilitiya i ustoychivnogo ravzitiya v Central Asia" and "Sovremennaya istoriya vzaimootnosheniy Uzbekistana i stran Tsentralnoy Azii s vedushchimi gosudarstvami mira", A. Kyrgyzboev's "International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with Asian countries" and R. Farmanov , Q. Juraev 's books entitled " History of International Relations " reflect the international relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the history of its emergence and development [7].

In the historiography of the history of ecological cooperation, books, pamphlets, and scientific articles that cover the socio-economic situation that has arisen in the Aral Sea region, as well as certain aspects of Uzbekistan 's cooperation with international organizations , including those of the countries of the region , are of particular importance . The book "Essays on Foreign Historiography of the Modern History of the Republic of Karakalpakstan" by B.A. Kochanov, T.A. Ametov, Y.B. Genzhemuratov, S.B. Kochanov, the monograph "The Environmental Situation in Uzbekistan and Its Social Problems (Second Half of the 20th Century - Beginning of the 21st Century)" by S.R. Davletov[8], "Ethnocultural Aspects of Environmental Problems of the Aral Sea Region" by R. Balliyeva, "The Role of the GEF Agency in Improving the Environmental Situation in the Lower Amu Darya Region" by S.R. Davletov[9], "The Role of International Projects in Solving Social and Environmental Problems in the Aral Sea Region" by O.B. Abdymuminov[11] also highlight the environmental problems that have arisen in the Aral Sea and the Aral Sea region. problems, cooperation with international organizations in their elimination, achievements in this regard, and issues that need to be resolved in the future are covered. The *second group also includes foreign* publications that cover some aspects of cooperation between the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea and the Central Asian Regional Ecological Center .

R. Alimov's monograph "Central Asia: Common Interests" is devoted to the main aspects of the security problem in Central Asia, the geopolitics of some world powers in the region, while Sh. Arifkhanov's book analyzes the geopolitical situation, prospects for solving the main problems of regional integration , and attempts to create a more stable environment for ensuring security in Central Asia . The studies of U. Hasanov, F. Tolipov, R. Farmanov, K. Juraev, I. Bobokulov, I. Mavlyanov, and M. Bakhadirov analyze the main directions and essence of geopolitical changes

in Central Asia, provide a framework for the formation of a national security strategy for Uzbekistan and the countries of the region, a classification of existing problems, and threats.

Studies related to Central Asia were carried out by historians from the CIS countries, primarily by Russian researchers - A.Akimov, V.Belokrinskiy, I. Zvyagelskaya, A.Bogaturov, A.Kurtov, A.Perepelkina, E.Kozozhkina, D. Trofimova, S.Panarina, E.Safronova, O.Tikhonova, A.Kazantseva, S.Bespalova, A.Vlasov, M.Starchak. In their works, analyzed the geopolitical situation, the political position of the states, the socio-economic development and foreign political relations of the Central Asian states. However, most of these studies are one-sided and focus on political aspects[12].

Studied the specific features of systemic human change and sustainable development in Uzbekistan over the past 25 years of independence. It examines the initial conditions in the newly independent states of Central Asia and the economic, social, and environmental processes that emerged during the subsequent transition period from a comparative perspective [13]. Particular attention is paid to the "Uzbek model." The positive impact of economic reforms on sustainable development, the main trends in the development of demography and labor resources, targeted work on education, healthcare, the environment, housing, and social protection of the population are studied.

Conclusion. In fact, one of the urgent issues for the countries of Central Asia, especially the Republic of Uzbekistan, today is strengthening a healthy ecological environment, transitioning to a "green economy", combating climate change, desertification, biodiversity loss and other environmental problems. In this regard, studying the environmental aspects of the country's domestic and foreign policy is of great importance.

Analysis of the level of study of the topic shows that the history of the establishment and development of international ecological relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan has not yet been comprehensively studied in Uzbekistan and abroad in a separate historical context. Therefore, it is advisable to further strengthen the study of the aspects of international cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to ecology and environmental protection, and to introduce the results of current research in various areas, including foreign research, into this process.

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